

23rd ISFC ISoFT'23

Québec City, July 23-28, 2023

23rd International Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry &
9th International Symposium on Fluorous Technologies

SYMPOSIUM PROGRAM

isfc2023.org
isoft2023.org

Meeting Rooms Floor Layout

- Registration Desk
- Speaker Ready Desk

- Parallel sessions rooms

- Plenary (main) session room

- Exhibition Hall
- Lunch
- Coffee Break
- Poster sessions

Program at a Glance

Sunday, July 23, 2023		Room
16:30 - 20:00	Registration	Hall 2000
17:30 - 17:45	Opening Ceremony	2000A
17:45 - 18:30	Plenary session - Alain Demourgues	2000A
18:30 - 21:30	WELCOME RECEPTION	Espace Urbain
Monday, July 24, 2023		
07:30 - 19:00	Registration	Hall 2000
08:30 - 09:15	Plenary session - Franziska Schoenebeck	2000A
09:20 - 10:20	Parallel sessions	See program
10:20 - 11:00	Coffee Break & Exhibition	2000BC
11:00 - 12:20	Parallel sessions	See program
12:20 - 13:40	Lunch	2000BC
13:40 - 15:00	Parallel sessions	See program
15:00 - 15:40	Coffee Break & Exhibition	2000BC
15:40 - 17:00	Parallel sessions	See program
17:05 - 17:50	Plenary session - Ellen Sletten	2000A
18:00 - 20:30	Poster session	2000BC
Tuesday, July 25, 2023		
08:00 - 18:00	Registration	Hall 2000
08:30 - 09:15	Plenary session - Pierangelo Metrangolo	2000A
09:20 - 10:20	Parallel sessions	See program
10:20 - 11:00	Coffee Break & Exhibition	2000BC
11:00 - 12:20	Parallel sessions	See program
12:20 - 13:40	Lunch	2000BC

13:40 - 15:20	Parallel sessions	See program
15:20 - 15:50	Group Photo	Hall 400
15:50 - 16:20	Coffee Break & Exhibition	2000BC
16:20 - 17:20	In memory of István T. Horváth	2000A
17:20 - 18:10	Plenary session - Marie-Pierre Krafft (ISoFT award)	2000A

Wednesday, July 26, 2023

08:30 - 20:00	ONE-DAY EXCURSION	
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Thursday, July 27, 2023

08:00 - 17:30	Registration	Hall 2000
08:30 - 09:15	Plenary session - Beate Kokschi	2000A
09:20 - 10:20	Parallel sessions	See program
10:20 - 11:00	Coffee Break & Exhibition	2000BC
11:00 - 12:20	Parallel sessions	See program
12:20 - 13:40	Lunch	2000BC
13:40 - 14:40	Parallel sessions	See program
14:40 - 15:20	Coffee Break & Exhibition	2000BC
15:20 - 16:20	Parallel sessions	See program
16:25 - 18:10	Moissan session - David O'Hagan and Véronique Gouverneur	2000A
18:45 - 00:00	BANQUET	VOLTIGEUR DE QUÉBEC ARMOURY

Friday, July 28, 2023

08:00 - 12:00	Registration	Hall 2000
08:15 - 09:15	Plenary session - Sensuki Ogoshi (Masato Ohashi)	2000A
09:20 - 10:40	Parallel sessions	See program
10:40 - 11:20	Coffee Break	Hall 2000
11:20 - 12:05	Plenary session - Thomas Braun	2000A
12:05 - 12:20	Closing Words	2000A
12:20 - 13:00	Departure	

**ISFC ISOFT 2023
Secretariat**

isfc2023@conferium.com or
isoft2023@conferium.com

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Welcoming Message

Dear Colleagues,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we welcome you to the joint 23rd International Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry and 9th International Symposium on Fluorous Technologies.

This year marks the 23rd triennial ISFC meeting and the 3rd joint meeting with the biennial ISoFT('23) conference series. Since their inceptions, both series of prestigious conferences have provided forums for large numbers of international researchers from academia, research institutes, and industry who have interests that span a broad spectrum of fundamental and applied fluorine chemistry that are of current importance to this multidisciplinary field.

Conference participants are from 29 countries and the conference program consists of plenary (10) and invited (99) lectures by internationally known speakers from academia and industry. Contributed oral presentations (75) and posters (83) will also provide participants with opportunities to disseminate their most recent research and to become acquainted with current developments among the diversity of fields that are characteristic of fundamental and applied fluorine chemistry. These include contributions from synthetic/structural organic and inorganic chemistry, materials science, fluorous technologies, and quantum chemistry.

The conference venue, the Québec City Convention Centre, is located in the heart of Québec City and is surrounded by numerous attractions—including the historic district of Old Québec, designated a World Heritage Site by UNESCO in 1985. Québec City, the only fortified city in the Americas north of Mexico, was founded in 1608 by Samuel de Champlain and is located on the left bank of the St. Lawrence River near the mouth of the St. Charles River. It has a remarkable history, first as the fortress capital of New France from 1608 to 1759, and later as the capital of Lower Canada under British rule. Since the confederation (1867), Québec City has served as the capital of “la belle province” and the home of the l'Assemblée Nationale du Québec. The city is located near several national and provincial parks, which ready access to wildlife and spectacular natural scenery. Québec City also affords access to cultural sites of the indigenous people, the “Nation Huronne-Wendat”, a community within Québec City.

We are looking forward to an outstanding program with stimulating scientific discussions and providing you with the opportunity to experience Québécois and Canadian history, culture, and the natural beauty of our country.

The 23rd ISFC-ISoFT ('23) Organizing Committee:

Chadron M. Friesen
Trinity Western University

Michael Gerken
University of Lethbridge

Jean-François Paquin
Université Laval

Gary J. Schrobilgen
McMaster University

Committees

Conference Chairs

Chadron M. Friesen - Trinity Western University

Michael Gerken - University of Lethbridge

Jean-François Paquin - Université Laval

Gary J. Schrobilgen - McMaster University

Organizing Committee

Francis Beaulieu - OmegaChem

Guillaume Bélanger-Chabot - Université Laval

Denis Giguère - Université Laval

Jennifer Love - University British Columbia

Christine Le - York University

Robert G. Syvret - Electronic Fluorocarbons

Neil Vasdev - University of Toronto

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Plenary Speakers

Thomas Braun

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Presenting on Friday, July 28, 2023

Alain Demourgues

Université de Bordeaux, France
Presenting on Sunday, July 23, 2023

Véronique Gouverneur

University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Presenting on Thursday, July 27, 2023

Beate Koksich

Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Presenting on Thursday, July 27, 2023

Marie-Pierre Krafft

Université de Stratsbourg, France
Presenting on Tuesday, July 25, 2023

Pierangelo Metrangolo

Politecnico di Milano, Italy
Presenting on Tuesday, July 25, 2023

Sensuki Ogoshi

Osaka University, Japan

Presented by Masato Ohashi

Masato Ohashi

Osaka University, Japan

Presenting on Friday, July 28, 2023

David O'Hagan

University of St. Andrews, United Kingdom

Presenting on Thursday, July 27, 2023

Franziska Schoenebeck

RWTH Aachen University, Germany

Presenting on Monday, July 24, 2023

Ellen Sletten

University of California, United States

Presenting on Monday, July 24, 2023

General Information

VENUE

Québec City Convention Centre
900 Boulevard Honoré-Mercier
Québec, QC G1R 5H9 Canada

PARKING

There are many underground parking spaces close to the Centre. More specifically, Marie-Guyart complex, Place Québec, Delta Hotel and finally the Place D'Youville parking lot all linked by underground connections. These lots operate 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

INTERNET ACCESS / MOBILE PHONE

Free internet facilities are available to all participants in the conference venue. During the meetings, please turn off your mobile phone or set it to mute.

Wifi: Centre_des_congrès

Password: Congres1996

REGISTRATION

All participants should register at the Registration Desk to receive relevant Symposium materials. The Registration Desk is located in the Hall 2000 of the Convention Centre. It will be open at the conference venue at the following times:

Sunday, July 23	16:30-20:00
Monday, July 24	07:30-19:00
Tuesday, July 25	08:00-18:00
Thursday, July 27	08:00-17:30
Friday, July 28	08:00-12:00

EXHIBITION HALL

Monday, July 24	10:30-20:30
Tuesday, July 25	10:20-16:30
Thursday, July 27	10:20-15:30

NAME BADGE

Please wear your name badge at all times. This will ensure your access to the symposium rooms and Exhibition Hall.

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

An official Certificate of Attendance will be available on demand.

DISCLAIMER

The ISFC ISoFT 2023 secretariat and organizers cannot assume liability for personal accidents, loss of or damage to private property of participants, and accompanying persons, either during or directly arising from the ISFC ISoFT 2023 Symposium. Participants should make their own arrangement with respect to health and travel insurance.

SECURITY & SAFETY

Please do not leave bags and luggage unattended at any time, whether inside or outside session rooms.

SPEAKER READY DESK

All speakers must check in the presentation room to upload their presentation 15 minutes before the start of their session. The volunteer will be available to answer your questions and to help you upload your presentation from your USB memory stick. Before your session, you can also stop by the registration desk and test your presentation at the Speaker Ready Desk, where one computer identical to the one in the presentation room will be available for testing.

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Exhibition

Exhibition Booths

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OAKWOOD PRODUCTS INC	3
AVANTOR / BUSHI	6

Entrance

Fluorine Chemistry in Ukraine

In 1948, Kyiv State University Professor and Academician Andrey Kiprianov (one of the major contributors to the theory of color of organic compounds), made an ambitious request to his graduate student Lev Yagupolskii to try something totally new as the subject of his Ph.D. dissertation research. He suggested that Yagupolskii undertake the then unknown chemistry of fluoroorganic compounds, in particular heterocyclic derivatives. In addition, Prof. Kiprianov suggested that his student also think about a less ambitious backup project because the chances of success in the uncharted waters of fluoroorganic chemistry were next to nothing. As it turned out, Lev Yagupolskii's dissertation laid the groundwork for the development of fluoroorganic chemistry in Ukraine.

The results obtained by Lev Yagupolskii in the course of his Ph.D. work, and by his group in the ensuing years, clearly underscored the scientific importance of fluoroorganic chemistry as a distinct discipline, which in 1965 resulted in the establishment of the Department of Fluoroorganic Compounds within the Institute of Organic Chemistry of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences, Kyiv, Ukraine. From that time onwards, Professor Lev Yagupolskii headed a full-scale research program in various areas of fluoroorganic chemistry that spawned new research groups throughout Ukraine and gained national and international prominence. In 1988 Professor Lev Yagupolskii was succeeded by his son, Yurii, as Head of the Department, however, Lev continued research work and mentoring Ph.D. students until the final day of his life. Lev Yagupolskii's research family includes 87 Ph.D. and 10 D.Sc. professionals who contributed their talents to numerous discoveries and the establishment of the Ukrainian brand of fluorine chemistry. Major milestones have been summarized in an article published in 2010 by Prof. Yurii Yagupolskii (Journal of Fluorine Chemistry 131 (2010) 123–126.

The organizers of the 23rd ISFC-ISoFT'23 have organized a special session entitled "Fluorine Chemistry in Ukraine" that is dedicated to Ukrainian Fluorine Chemists at Risk. This session honors the bravery and tenacity of Ukrainian scientists in general who strive daily to maintain their research programs under the perilous conditions of an ongoing war on their soil. The session consists of five invited lectures delivered virtually by Professors Yurii L. Yagupolskii, Yuriy G. Schermolovich, Pavel K. Mykhailiuk, Igor Gerus, and Olexander Grygorenko. Profs. Yagupolskii and Schermolovich served as the Co-Chairs for the 18th European Symposium on Fluorine held in Kyiv, Ukraine in 2016.

The following donors provided financial support for the special session "Fluorine Chemistry in Ukraine": Fonds de recherche du Québec, Université Laval, Trinity Western University, University of Lethbridge, Plantbiosis and a number of conference attendees.

Oral Presentations

Sunday, July 23, 2023

WELCOMING WORDS

ROOM: 2000A

17:30 - 17:45 **WELCOMING WORDS**

PLENARY SESSION - ALAIN DEMOURGUES - SPONSORED BY FLUOREK LIMITED

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Michael Gerken, University of Lethbridge, Canada

17:45 - 18:30 **THE GROWING CHALLENGE IN ASSOCIATING FLUORINE WITH
ADDITIONAL ANIONS IN INORGANIC CHEMISTRY TO GET NOVEL
MATERIALS FOR ENERGY, CATALYSIS AND OPTICS**
Alain Demourgues, ICMCB-CNRS-University of Bordeaux, France

Sunday

Monday, July 24, 2023

PLENARY SESSION - FRANZISKA SCHOENEBECK - SPONSORED BY CHEMOURS

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Herbert W. Roesky, University of Göttingen, Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Germany

8:30 - 9:15 **NEW MOLECULAR MOTIFS AND HOW TO MAKE THEM: N-CF₃ AND BEYOND**
Franziska Schoenebeck, Franziska Schoenebeck, Professor, RWTH Aachen University, Germany

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 01

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Norio Shibata, Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan

9:20 - 9:40 **ASYMMETRIC CATALYTIC SYNTHESIS OF FLUORO-ORGANIC COMPOUNDS**
Mark Gandelman, Technion - Israel Institute of Technology, Israel

9:40 - 10:00 **STEREOSELECTIVE PREPARATION OF CF₃-CONTAINING MOLECULES**
Dominique Cahard, CNRS, France

10:00 - 10:20 **SYNTHESIS OF MULTIVICINAL INTER-HALIDES FROM LEVOGLUCOSAN**
Olivier Lessard, Université Laval, Canada
Danny Lainé, Denis Giguère

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 02

ROOM: 207

Chair: Günter Haufe, University of Münster, Germany

9:20 - 9:40 **CATALYTIC ENANTIOSELECTIVE SYNTHESIS OF FLUORO, TRIFLUOROMETHYL AND DIFLUOROMETHYL CYCLOPROPANES**
Philippe Jubault, UMR 6014 COBRA, France

9:40 - 10:00 **S(VI) FLUORIDES AS SYNTHONS IN ORGANIC SYNTHESIS**
Nicholas Ball, Pomona College, United States of America

10:00 - 10:20 **INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ACCESSING FLUOROALKYL ARENES AND HETEROARENES**
Ryan Altman, Purdue University, United States of America

COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Sebastian Hasenstab-Riedel, FU Berlin, Germany

9:20 - 9:40 **COMPUTATIONAL FLUORINE CHEMISTRY ACROSS THE PERIODIC TABLE**
David Dixon, University of Alabama, United States of America

9:40 - 10:00 **REDEFINING THE BONDED ATOM, ITS CHARGE, ENERGY, ELECTRONEGATIVITY AND CHEMICAL HARDNESS**
Martin Rahm, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden
Stefano Racioppi, **Francesco Sessa**, **Álvaro Lobato**

10:00 - 10:20 **APPLICATIONS OF THEORETICAL CALCULATIONS TO UNDERSTAND CONFORMATION AND NON CONVALENT INTERACTIONS IN ORGANOFLUORINE COMPOUNDS**
Rodrigo Cormanich, University of Campinas, Brazil
Zeoly Lucas A., **Rodrigo Cormanich**

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 01

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Berthold Hoge, Bielefeld University, Germany

9:20 - 9:40 **C-F BOND ACTIVATION @ NI(NHC)2**
Udo Radius, Institute for Inorganic Chemistry, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany

9:40 - 10:00 **A STABLE COMPLEX OF ENDOTHERMIC OCLF, F5IR—OCLF; AND THE MIXED-OXIDATION-STATE IRIIDIUM (+5,+6) SALT, [CLO2]2[CYCLO-{{(M-O)IRF4}3]**
Mark Bortolus, McMaster University, Canada
James Goettel, **Helene Mercier**, **Gary Schrobilgen**

10:00 - 10:20 **INTRODUCING THE PERFLUORINATED CP* LIGAND INTO COORDINATION CHEMISTRY**
Moritz Malischewski, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 03

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Thierry Billard, CNRS-University of Lyon, France

11:00 - 11:20 **DECARBOXYLATIVE METHODS FOR INTRODUCING FLUOROMETHOXY AND FLUOROALKYL GROUPS**

Lukas Goossen, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany

Jonas Göbel

11:20 - 11:40 **A PHOTOCATALYTIC APPROACH TO MONOFLUOROALKENES: ADDITION OF CARBON RADICALS TO ALLYLIC DIFLUORIDES**

Jean-Denys Hamel, University of Lethbridge, Canada

Ty Dudas, Jean-Denys Hamel

11:40 - 12:00 **ADVANCES IN THE VISIBLE LIGHT PHOTOCATALYTIC HYDRODEFUORINATION OF ARENES**

Jimmie Weaver, Oklahoma State University, United States of America

Jimmie Weaver

12:00 - 12:20 **PHOTOCATALYZED HYDROAMINODIFLUOROALKYLATION OF ALKENES**
Thierry Lequeux, University of Caen, LCMT, France

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 04

ROOM: 207

Chair: Henryk Koroniak, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland

11:00 - 11:20 **STEREOSELECTIVE PALLADIUM-CATALYZED C-F BOND ACTIVATION OF GEM-DIFLUOROALKENES FOR MULTIFARIOUS C-C AND C-HETEROATOM BOND CONSTRUCTION**

Gavin Chit Tsui, Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

11:20 - 11:40 **CONTINUOUS-FLOW PENTAFLUOROALKYLATION USING HFC-125**

Juji Sumii, Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan

Hiroto Iwasaki, Yamato Fujihira, Norio Shibata

11:40 - 12:00 **HYDROGEN BONDING-MEDIATED FORMAL C'F INSERTION INTO ACTIVATED ALKYL FLUORIDES FORMING GEM-DIFLUORO COMPOUNDS**

Arushi Garg, Newcastle University, United Kingdom

Nils Gerwien, Matthew N. Hopkinson

12:00 - 12:20 **SYNTHETIC STRATEGIES EXPLOITING FLUORIDE-ENABLED REACTIVITY**
Christine Le, York University, Canada

MATERIALS - 01

ROOM: 2101

Chair: **Olga Boltalina**, Colorado State University, United States Of America

11:00 - 11:20 **PREPARATION OF F-DIAMANE-LIKE NANOSHEETS VIA EXFOLIATION**

Marc Dubois, Université Clermont Auvergne, France
Marie Colin, Sam Chen

11:20 - 11:40 **FLUORINATION OF CARBON BLACK WITH ELEMENTAL FLUORINE AS EFFECTIVE SUPPRESSION OF SHUTTLE EFFECT IN LITHIUM-SULFUR BATTERIES**

Piergiorgio Marziani, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
Sebastian Risse, Luca Magagnin, Maurizio Sansotera

11:40 - 12:00 **UNIVERSAL FUNCTIONALIZATION STRATEGY WITH PERFLUOROPOLYETHERS FOR THE FAMILY OF CARBON-BASED NANOSTRUCTURED MATERIALS**

Maurizio Sansotera, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
Eugenio Gibertini, Claudia L. Bianchi, Gianlorenzo Bussetti, Luca Nobili, Luca Magagnin

12:00 - 12:20 **UNUSUAL CHANGES OF C-H BONDS IN THE FLUORINATED COMPOUNDS FROM NEUTRON DIFFRACTION**

Norman Lu, Taipei Tech, Taiwan (Republic of China)
Vijayanath Elakkat, Eskedar Tessema

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 02

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: **Kazuhiko Matsumoto**, Kyoto University, Japan

11:00 - 11:20 **PERFLUOROALKYLAMIDES AND PERFLUOROALKYLIMIDES COORDINATION COMPOUNDS AND IONIC LIQUIDS**

Maik Finze, University of Wuerzburg, Germany

11:20 - 11:40 **WEAKLY AND EVEN WEAKER COORDINATING ANIONS: TUNING STABILITY AND REACTIVITY**

Michal Jadwiszczak, University of Warsaw, Poland
Joanna Dobkiewicz, Magdalena Abramowicz, Przemyslaw Malinowski

11:40 - 12:00 **UPSCALED SYNTHESIS OF THE WEAKLY COORDINATING ANION [CHB11F11]⁻ AND ITS APPLICATIONS**

Jan Kulenkampff, University of Freiburg, Department of inorganic and analytical Chemistry, Germany
Christian Armbruster, Celine Regnat, Tina Wienold, Ingo Krossing

12:00 - 12:20 **FLUROHYDROGENATE IONIC LIQUIDS**

Rika Hagiwara, Kyoto University, Japan
Kazuhiko Matsumoto

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 05

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Gerald (Gb) Hammond, University of Louisville, United States Of America

13:40 - 14:00 **ELECTROSYNTHESIS AND ORGANOFLUORINE CHEMISTRY: AN INTERESTING PARTNERSHIP**

Thomas Poisson, UMR 6014 COBRA, France

14:00 - 14:20 **LATE-STAGE ELECTROCHEMICAL FLUORINATION OF HIGH-VALUE PROLINE DERIVATIVES**

Patrick Ryan, University of New South Wales (UNSW), Australia
Giancarlo Pascali, Luke Hunter

14:20 - 14:40 **ELECTROCHEMICAL NUCLEOPHILIC BENZYLIC C(SP³)-H FLUORINATION**

Alexander Atkins, Univeristy of Bristol, United Kingdom
Atul Chaturvedi, **Albert Rowett**, **David Heard**, **Joseph Tate**, **Alastair Lennox**

14:40 - 15:00 **PHOTOREDOX CATALYSIS AND ELECTROCHEMISTRY: COMPLEMENTARY STRATEGIES FOR THE TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION OF OLEFINS**

Géraldine Masson, CNRS, France

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 01

ROOM: 207

Chair: David O'Hagan, University of St Andrews, United Kingdom

13:40 - 14:00 **THE INFLUENCE OF ALIPHATIC FLUORINATION ON LIPOPHILICITY AND ON MEMBRANE PARTITIONING**

Bruno Linclau, Ghent University, Belgium

14:00 - 14:20 **OUT OF THE ORDINARY: BIODEGRADATION OF ORGANOFLUORINE POLLUTANTS WITH COMMON-OR-GARDEN MICROBES**

Cormac Murphy, University College Dublin, Ireland

14:20 - 14:40 **FLUORINE-INDUCED PSEUDO-ANOMERIC EFFECT IN CYCLOHEXANES**

Bruno Piscelli, University of Campinas, Brazil
David O'Hagan, **Rodrigo Cormanich**

14:40 - 15:00 **CARBOHYDRATE APPROACH TO MULTIVICINAL FLUORINATED AND INTER-HALIDE STEREOCENTERS**

Denis Giguère, Université Laval, Canada

ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY - 01

ROOM: 2101

Chair: David Vicic, Lehigh University, United States

13:40 - 14:00 **CALL A COPPER! FLUOROALKYLATION OF ORGANIC ELECTROPHILES USING FLUOROALKENES**

Tom Baker, University of Ottawa, Canada

Luana Porto, Nicholas Andrella, Behnaz Ghaffari, Christian Ehm

14:00 - 14:20 **SUPERFLUOROMETHYL; FLUOROMETHYLATION MADE EASY**

Alexander Gisnapp, Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich, Germany

Marco Reichel, Dominik Leitz, Andreas J. Kornath, Konstantin

Karaghiosoff

14:20 - 14:40 **THE TRIFLUOROMETHYL SILVER(III) MOIETY AS A PLATFORM FOR HIGHLY UNUSUAL ORGANOMETALLIC COMPOUNDS**

Miguel Baya, Universidad de Zaragoza - CSIC, Spain

Daniel Joven-Sancho, Luca Demonti, Antonio Martín, Nathalie Saffon-

Merceron, Noel Nebra, Babil Menjón

Monday

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 03

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: David Dixon, The University of Alabama, United States Of America

13:40 - 14:00 **HALOGEN BOND ALLOWS FOR ANHYDROUS FLUORIDE ANIONS**

Giuseppe Resnati, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
Susantha Nayak, Andrea Daolio

14:00 - 14:20 **CHLORINE AND FLUORINE IN PYRIDINE HALONIUM CHEMISTRY**

Patrick Pröhm, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Sebastian Riedel

14:20 - 14:40 **TETRACOORDINATE [SF₃]⁺ ADDUCTS WITH ORGANIC BASES**

Felix O'Donnell, University of Lethbridge, Canada
Yoyo Yao, Stacey Wetmore, Michael Gerken

14:40 - 15:00 **A NEW MOTIF IN HALOGEN BONDING: COOPERATIVE INTERMOLECULAR S'BR...O, O...F, AND F...F ASSOCIATIONS IN THE CRYSTAL PACKING OF ALPHA,OMEGA-DI(SULFONYL BROMIDE) PERFLUOROALKANES**

Joseph Thrasher, Clemson University, Department of Chemistry, United States of America
David Helm, Megan Smart, Colin McMillen, Leah Casabianca, Rakesh Sachdeva, Catherine Urick, London Wilson, Joseph Thrasher

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 06

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Jinbo Hu, Shanghai Institute of Organic Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China (People's Republic of)

15:40 - 16:00 **SILYL RADICAL-MEDIATED CROSS-COUPLING REACTIONS OF ORGANIC FLUORIDES**

Norio Shibata, Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan

16:00 - 16:20 **A JOURNEY WITH DNTFB IN FLUORINE CHEMISTRY**

Clémence Bonnefoy, ICBMS - Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France
Clément Delobel, Emmanuel Chefdeville, Armen Panossian, Gilles Hanquet, Frédéric Leroux, Fabien Toulgoat, Thierry Billard

16:20 - 16:40 **ACCESS TO FLUORINATED MOLECULES BY C-H FUNCTIONALIZATION**

Floriane Doche, Laboratoire COBRA, France
Tatiana Besset, Thomas Poisson, Davide Audisio

16:40 - 17:00 **LATE-STAGE FUNCTIONALIZATIONS**

Tobias Ritter, Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 02

ROOM: 207

Chair: Bruno Linclau, Ghent University, Belgium

15:40 - 16:00 **BIOENGINEERING WITH FLUORINATED AMINO ACIDS: FLUORINE AS AN ELEMENT OF LIFE**

Ned Budisa, University of Manitoba, Canada

16:00 - 16:20 **¹⁹F SOLID-STATE NMR TO STUDY THE INTERACTION OF ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES WITH BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES**

Kiran Kumar, Université du Québec à Montréal, Department of Chemistry, Canada

Raphaël Gauthier, Marius Mamone, Alexandre A. Arnold, Jean-François Paquin, Dror E. Warschawski, Isabelle Marcotte

16:20 - 16:40 **SNAR REACTIONS OF FLUOROBENZENES - CLICK-REACTIONS FOR BIOCONJUGATIONS**

Frederik Diness, Roskilde University, Denmark

Niklas H. Fischer, Sergei Nikitin, Ahmed Embaby, Morten Meldal, Frederik Diness

ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY - 02

ROOM: 2101

Chair: R. Tom Baker, University of Ottawa, Canada

15:40 - 16:00 **SOLVATED NICKEL COMPLEXES AS STOICHIOMETRIC AND CATALYTIC TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION AGENTS**

David Vacic, Lehigh University, United States of America
Scott Shreiber

16:00 - 16:20 **DIFLUOROCARBENE INSERTION INTO THE METAL-CARBON BOND: SUPPRESSING ALPHA-FLUORIDE ELIMINATION WITH A GOLD(I) SYSTEM**

Zeng Rong Wong, University of California, Berkeley, United States of America
Binh Mai, Alexander Kvitsinski, Willi Berg, Peng Liu, F. Dean Toste

16:20 - 16:40 **HYDROGEN BONDING-CONTROLLED GOLD CATALYSIS: THE EFFECTS OF HYDROFLUORIC ACID AND HEXAFLUOROISOPROPANOL**

Nikolaos V. Tzouras, Ghent University, Department of Chemistry, Belgium
Raphaël Gauthier, Jean-François Paquin, Georgios C. Vougioukalakis, Steven P. Nolan

16:40 - 17:00 **NOVEL PATHWAY OF HYDROSILYLATION ACCESSED BY HIGHLY LEWIS-ACIDIC CALCIUM CATALYST**

Magdalena Grochowska-Tatarczak, University of Warsaw, Poland
Ewa Nawrocka, Krzysztof Kazmierczuk, Przemyslaw Malinowski

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 04

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: **Moritz Malischewski**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

15:40 - 16:00 **BROMINE DIOXIDE FLUORIDE, BRO₂F, AND BROMINE DIOXIDE, BRO₂**
Konrad Seppelt, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

Patrick Pröhm

16:00 - 16:20 **EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF WEAK I-F BONDS TO ACCESS NOVEL I(III) OXIDANTS**

Tania T., La Trobe University, Australia

Lachlan Sharp-Bucknall, Jason Dutton

16:20 - 16:40 **EFFECT OF FLUORINE-INDUCED DIPOLE MOMENTS IN SELF-ASSEMBLED MONOLAYERS**

Andreas Terfort, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany

Andreas Terfort, Michael Zharnikov

16:40 - 17:00 **ATTEMPTED SYNTHESIS OF XEF₅M(XF₆)₃ SALTS (M²⁺ = CU, NI; X⁵⁺ = CR, NB, TA, RU, RH, RE, OS, IR, PT, AU, AS)**

Zoran Mazej, Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

Evgeny Goreschnik

PLENARY SESSION - ELLEN SLETTEN - SPONSORED BY APOLLO SCIENTIFIC

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: **Giuseppe Resnati**, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

17:05 - 17:50 **HARNESSING THE BIOORTHOGONALITY OF FLUORINE FOR ADVANCED BIOMATERIALS**

Ellen Sletten, UCLA, United States of America

Tuesday, July 25, 2023

PLENARY SESSION - PIERANGELO METRANGOLO - SPONSORED BY SOLVAY SPECIALITY POLYMERS ITALY SPA

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Bruno Ameduri, Institute Charles Gerhardt Montpellier, France

8:30 - 9:15 **TAILOR-MADE DESIGN OF ¹⁹F-MRI PROBES BASED ON BRANCHED FLUORINATED RESIDUES**
Pierangelo Metrangolo, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 07

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Thomas Lectka

9:20 - 9:40 **UTILITARIAN FLUORINE REAGENTS: A PROGRESS REPORT**
Gerald B. Hammond, University of Louisville, United States of America

9:40 - 10:00 **DETERMINING THE ACIDITY OF HF-DERIVED FLUORINATING REAGENTS**
Mélissa Longuet, IC2MP, Université de Poitiers, France
Kassandra Vitse, Agnès Martin-Mingot, Frédéric Guégan, Bastien Michelet, Sébastien Thibaudeau

10:00 - 10:20 **SUPERELECTROPHILIC ACTIVATION TO ENRICH MOLECULAR CHEMICAL SPACE**
Sébastien Thibaudeau, Université de Poitiers, UMR-CNRS 7285, IC2MP, France

Tuesday

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 08

ROOM: 207

Chair: Petr Beier, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Czech Republic

9:20 - 9:40 **5-ENDO-TRIG CYCLIZATION OF FLUORO ALKENES: SYNTHESIS OF FLUORINATED HETEROLE DERIVATIVES**
Junji Ichikawa, Sagami Chemical Research Institute, Japan

9:40 - 10:00 **LEWIS ACID-MEDIATED TRANSFORMATION OF N-FLUOROALKYL-1,2,3-TRIAZOLES**
Lukas Janecky, Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic
Petr Beier

10:00 - 10:20 **ACTIVATED VINYL FLUORIDES IN DIELS-ALDER REACTIONS**
Günter Haufe, University of Münster, Organic Chemistry Institute, Germany
Michael Essers

FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY - 01

ROOM: 2101

Chair: John Gladysz, Texas A&M University, United States Of America

9:20 - 9:40 **COORDINATION CHEMISTRY IN/ON FLUOROUS PHASES APPLIED TO PURIFICATION AND SENSING PROCESSES**
Jean-Marc Vincent, CNRS-University of Bordeaux, France

9:40 - 10:00 **RECYCLABLE FLUOROUS ORGANOCATALYSTS IN ASYMMETRIC SYNTHESIS**
Wei Zhang, University of Massachusetts Boston, United States of America

10:00 - 10:20 **SHORT-CHAIN MULTIBRANCHED PERFLUOROALKYL DERIVATIVES AS VERSATILE TOOLS FOR THE DESIGN OF FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS**
Gabriella Cavallo, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
Leonardo Leccioli, Anastasios Stergiou, Pierangelo Metrangolo

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 05

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Maik Finze, University of Würzburg, Germany

9:20 - 9:40 **INTERACTIONS OF FLUORIDE ION AND ALCOHOLS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN ISOPROPANOL AND HEXAFLUOROISOPROPANOL SYSTEMS**

Kazuhiko Matsumoto, Graduate School of Energy Science, Kyoto University, Japan

Nozomi Yoneda, Haruka Iyama, Yoshiki Ishii, Kohei Tada, Rika Hagiwara

9:40 - 10:00 **A FLUORSPAR ALTERNATIVE? JOURNEY TOWARDS A TERMINAL CALCIUM-MONOFUORIDE**

Mathias A. Ellwanger, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

Job Struijs, Veronique Gouverneur, Simon Aldridge

10:00 - 10:20 **IMIDAZOLIUM FLUORIDE AS A REAGENT WITH COMPOUNDS OF GROUP 14 ELEMENTS**

Gasper Tavcar, Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

Jan Gnidovec, Evelin Gruden, Jernej Iskra, Jaroslav Kvicala, Melita Tramsek

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 09

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Emmanuel Magnier, Institut Lavoisier de Versailles UMR CNRS 8180, France

11:00 - 11:20 **REGIO- AND STEREOSELECTIVE HYDROELEMENTATION OF SF5 ALKYNES**

Vincent Bizet, CNRS UMR 7042 LIMA, France

11:20 - 11:40 **TETRAFLUORO(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)-6-SULFANYLETHANOL AND TETRAFLUORO(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)-6-SULFANYLETHANAMINES: MOLECULAR DYNAMICS AND DYNAMIC LIGHT SCATTERING STUDIES OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS AND THE INFLUENCE OF THOSE SOLUTIONS ON THE SECONDARY STRUCTURE OF MELITTIN**

John Welch, University at Albany, United States of America

Muqian Deng, John Welch

11:40 - 12:00 **TRIFLUOROMETHOXYLATION AND PENTAFLUROSULFANYLATION**

Feng-Ling Qing, Shanghai Institute of Organic Chemistry, China (People's Republic of)

12:00 - 12:20 **EXPLORING UNCHARTED CHEMICAL SPACE WITH THE SF5 GROUP AND ITS CONGENERS**

Cody Pitts, University of California, Davis, United States of America

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 03

ROOM: 207

Chair: Neil Vasdev, Centre for Addiction and Mental Health & University of Toronto, Canada

11:00 - 11:20 **18F-RADIOCHEMISTRY: REACTION DEVELOPMENT AND CLINICAL TRANSLATION**

Matthew Tredwell, Cardiff University, United Kingdom

11:20 - 11:40 **THE JOURNEY TO LATE-STAGE DIFLUOROMETHYLATIONS FOR MEDICAL IMAGING**

Chadron Friesen, Trinity Western University, Canada

11:40 - 12:00 **DEVELOPMENT OF A SIMPLE ONE-POT 18F-FLUOROMETHYLATION STRATEGY FOR THE LABELLING OF [18F]FMPEP-D2 FOR IMAGING THE CANNABINOID RECEPTOR 1**

Anna Pees, Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH), Canada
Neil Vasdev

12:00 - 12:20 **DESIGN, SYNTHESIS AND BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF CHEMICAL TOOLS FOR STUDYING GBA IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE**

Christopher Phenix, University of Saskatchewan, Canada
Aarnoud van der Spoel, Shusheng Wang, Morshed Chowdhury, Omid Tavassoly, Devin Brown, Leanne Carter

FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY - 02

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Gabriella Cavallo, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

11:00 - 11:20 **STABILIZATION OF THERAPEUTIC PEPTIDES AND BIOLOGICAL MATERIALS VIA FLUORINATION**

Krishna Kumar, Tufts University, United States of America

11:20 - 11:40 **PROBING THE LIMITS OF FLUOROUS INTERACTIONS: AUTOMATED GLYCAN SYNTHESIS WITH FLUOROUS TAGS IN BATCH AND FLOW SYSTEMS**

Nicola Pohl, Indiana University, United States of America

11:40 - 12:00 **A BIS-ACRIDINIUM MACROCYCLE AS MULTI-RESPONSIVE RECEPTOR AND SELECTIVE PHASE-TRANSFER AGENT OF PERYLENE**

Henri-Pierre Jacquot de Rouville, Université de Strasbourg - CNRS, France

12:00 - 12:20 **MODULAR SYNTHESIS OF SHRUBBY FLUOROUS LIGANDS**

Laszlo T. Mika, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary
Zoltán Medgyesi, Csaba Árvai, Laszlo T. Mika

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 06

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Joseph Thrasher, Clemson University, United States of America

11:00 - 11:20 **CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS OF FLUORINE**

Karl O. Christe, Loker Research Institute, University of Southern California, United States of America
David A. Dixon, Gabriel de Melo, Monica Vasiliu, Martin Moebs, Florian Kraus

11:20 - 11:40 **NEW POROUS INORGANIC FLUORIDES FOR THE STORAGE OF MOLECULAR FLUORINE F₂ BY CHEMISORPTION**

Valentine Camus-Genot, Institut des Molécules et Matériaux du Mans (IMMM), France
Amandine Guiet, Christophe Legein, Monique Body, Etienne Durand, Alain Demourgues, Annie Hémon-Ribaud, Sagrario Pascual, Cyrille Galven, Romain Moury, Vincent Maisonneuve, Jérôme Lhoste

11:40 - 12:00 **THE SIMONS PROCESS: NEW INSIGHTS BY THEORY AND EXPERIMENT**

Tilen Lindic, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Gene Senges, Sebastian Riedel, Beate Paulus

12:00 - 12:20 **THE CRYSTAL STRUCTURES OF F₂ AND NF₃ AND THE NOVEL [BR₃F₁₆] AND [(BRF₅)₆(HF₂)(H₂F₃)]₂ ANIONS**

Florian Kraus, Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany
Florian Kraus

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - UKRAINE

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Wojciech Grochala, Univ. Warsaw, CeNT, Poland

- 13:40 - 14:00 **ADVENTURE WITH TERT-PERFLUOROBUTYL GROUP IN AROMATICS WITH THE HAPPY END**
Yurii Yagupolskii, Institute of Organic Chemistry NAS of Ukraine, Ukraine
-
- 14:00 - 14:20 **PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF FLUORINE-CONTAINING SATURATED (HETERO)CYCLES**
Oleksandr Grygorenko, Taras Schevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine
Kostiantyn Melnykov, Serhii Holovach, Oleksandr Demchuk, Oleksandr Hryshchuk, Dmitriy Volocnyuk
-
- 14:20 - 14:40 **BETA-ALKOXYVINYL POLYFLUOROALKYL KETONES AS A POWERFUL SYNTHETIC TOOL IN FLUOROORGANIC CHEMISTRY**
Igor Gerus, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic and Petrochemistry
National Academy of Science of Ukraine, Ukraine
-
- 14:40 - 15:00 **MODERN FLUORINATED BUILDING BLOCKS FOR MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY**
Pavel Mykhailiuk, Enamine, Ukraine
Vadym Sham, Vasyl Ripenko, Volodymyr Ahunovych
-
- 15:00 - 15:20 **UNDEREXPLORED ORGANIC DERIVATIVES OF SII, SIV AND SVI FLUORIDES**
Yuriy Shermolovich, Institute of Organic Chemistry NAS of Ukraine, Ukraine
Sergiy Zasukha, Olexander Guzyr
-

Tuesday

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 04

ROOM: 207

Chair: Christopher Phenix, University of Saskatchewan, Canada

13:40 - 14:00 **FLUORINE-18 CHEMISTRY FROM BENCH TO BEDSIDE TO COMMUNITY**

Neil Vasdev, Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH) & University of Toronto, Canada

14:00 - 14:20 **HETEROCYCLIC FLUROSILANES: HYDROLYTIC STABILITY, FLUORINE ISOTOPE EXCHANGE AND DEVELOPMENT OF 18F-LABELED RADIOPHARMACEUTICALS**

Alexey Kostikov, McGill University, Montreal Neurological Institute, Canada

En Zhao, Thomas Singleton, Hyun Jun, Prashant Deore, Carl Estrada, Mohamed El-Zaria, Matthew Moran, Afaf Genady, Simon Edelmann, Darcy Burley, Luis Rafael Silva, Yusra Marfatia, Ayman Ibrahim, Andrea Armstrong, Patrick DeRoy, Alexandre Larivée, Christopher Waldmann, Saman Sadeghi, Jean-Philip Lumb

14:20 - 14:40 **A MECHANISTICALLY GUIDED APPROACH TO SUPPRESS PROTOBORONATION IN 19F/18F CU-CATALYZED FLUORINATION OF ARYLBORONIC ACIDS**

Jingkai Sun, University of Alberta, Canada
Carolin Jaworski, Ralf Schirrmacher, Dennis Hall

14:40 - 15:00 **SYNTHESIS OF A 18F-LABELED ALK2 INHIBITOR FOR NEUROIMAGING IN DIPG**

Melissa Chassé, Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH), Canada
Neil Vasdev

15:00 - 15:20 **18F RADIOCHEMISTRY: RECENT ADVANCES IN SYNTHETIC METHODOLOGIES**

Frank Wuest, University of Alberta, Canada

FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY - 03

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Nicola Pohl, Indiana University, United States Of America

13:40 - 14:00 **ON THE ATTACKS FROM REGULATORS ON PER- AND POLYFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES (PFASS): ARE FLUOROPOLYMERS SUSPICIOUS?**

Bruno Ameduri, ICGM, CNRS, France

Hisao Hori

14:00 - 14:20 **PREVENTING CONTAMINATION RELATED TO GLOBAL AND CLIMATE CHANGE USING KEY ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES**

Ana B. Pereiro, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal

María C. Naranjo, Julio E. Sosa, João M. M. Araújo

14:20 - 14:40 **FLUOROPOLYMER RECYCLING: SOLUTIONS FOR CIRCULARITY APPLIED TO FLUORINATED MATERIALS**

Stefano Millefanti, Solvay Materials, Italy

Marta Rosati, Maurizio Sansotera, Pierangelo Metrangolo

14:40 - 15:00 **EFFICIENT MINERALIZATION OF POLY(VINYLDENE FLUORIDE) AND RELATED COPOLYMERS USING SUPERHEATED WATER WITH ALKALINE REAGENT**

Hisao Hori, Kanagawa University, Japan

Jin Hamaura, Ryo Honma, Abdelatif Manseri, Bruno Ameduri

MATERIALS - 02

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Norman Lu, National Taipei University of Technology (Taipei Tech), Taiwan (Republic Of China)

13:40 - 14:00 **FLUORINATED MATERIAL AS POSITIVE ELECTRODES FOR LI- AND NA-ION BATTERIES**

Vincent Maisonneuve, IMMM CNRS, France

Annie Hémon-Ribaud, Marc Leblanc, Jérôme Lhoste, Jean-Marie

Tarascon, Vincent Maisonneuve

14:00 - 14:20 **OPTIMIZED ELECTRODE/ELECTROLYTE INTERFACE OF MWCNT-SNO₂ COMPOSITE THROUGH GAS-SOLID FLUORINATION**

Katia Guérin, Université Clermont Auvergne, Institut de Chimie de

Clermont-Ferrand, France

14:20 - 14:40 **IMPACT OF NI SUBSTITUTION IN A MIXED FE-CO RUTILE OXYFLUORIDE ON OER ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES**
Alexandre Terry, Kornienko Lab - Faculté des Arts et des Sciences - Campus MIL - Université de Montréal, Canada

14:40 - 15:00 **REVERSIBLE TRANSITION OF AN AMORPHOUS CU-AL OXYFLUORIDE INTO AN ACTIVE ELECTROCATALYST FOR NITRATE REDUCTION TO AMMONIA**
Amandine Guiet, IMMM, Le Mans Université, France

IN MEMORY OF ISTVÁN T. HORVÁTH

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Jean-Marc Vincent, CNRS - University of Bordeaux, France

16:20 - 16:50 **THIRTY YEARS OF INSPIRED FLUORINE-BASED CHEMISTRY; A TRIBUTE TO ISTVÁN T. HORVÁTH**
John A. Gladysz, Texas A&M University, United States of America

16:50 - 17:20 **HOW THE HORVÁTH PARADIGM, FLUOROUS BIPHASIC CATALYSIS, AFFECTED OXIDATION CHEMISTRY: SUCCESSES, CHALLENGES, AND A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE-A TRIBUTE**
Richard H. Fish, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, University of California, Berkeley, United States of America
Jean-Marc Vincent, Maria Contel, Gianluca Pozzi

PLENARY SESSION - MARIE-PIERRE KRAFFT (I. T. HORVÁTH FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGIES AWARD) - SPONSORED BY OAKWOOD PRODUCTS INC.

ROOM: 2000A

17:20 - 17:25 **INTRODUCTION**

17:25 - 18:10 **FLUOROCARBONS@INTERFACES: ACQUIRING FUNDAMENTAL KNOWLEDGE FOR APPLICATIONS IN MEDICINE AND ENERGY**
Marie Pierre Krafft, University of Strasbourg (CNRS), France

Thursday, July 27, 2023

PLENARY SESSION - BEATE KOKSCH - SPONSORED BY MAGRITEK INC.

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Günter Haufe, University of Münster, Germany

8:30 - 9:15 **CONSTRUCTION AND DEGRADATION OF FLUORINATED BIOPOLYMERS**
Beate Kokschi, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 10

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Frédéric Leroux, CNRS, France

9:20 - 9:40 **INITIAL INVESTIGATION OF THE INCORPORATION OF THE 1,1,2,2-TETRAFLUOROETHYL SUBSTITUENT INTO ORGANIC COMPOUNDS VIA PHOTOREDOX CHEMISTRY**
William Dolbier, University of Florida, United States of America
Xinjin Li

9:40 - 10:00 **SIMPLE SYNTHETIC METHODS OF DIFLUOROETHYL AND FLUOROVINYL ETHERS USING HALOTHANE**
Yukiko Karuo, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Setsunan University, Japan
Atsushi Tarui, Kazuyuki Sato, Kentaro Kawai, Masaaki Omote

10:00 - 10:20 **REACTIONS OF POLYFLUORINATED OLEFINS WITH FLUORINATED THIOKETONES**
Vlacheslav Petrov, Chemours, United States of America

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 05

ROOM: 207

Chair: John Welch, University at Albany, SUNY, United States

9:20 - 9:40 **THE C-F—AMIDE CARBONYL INTERACTION**
Thomas Lectka, Johns Hopkins, United States of America

9:40 - 10:00 **RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN ANTIMONY-BASED PLATFORMS FOR FLUORIDE SENSING AND TRAFFICKING**
Francois Gabbai, Texas A&M University, United States of America

10:00 - 10:20 **FLUORINATED AMINO ACIDS WITH OLEFINIC MOTIF AS POTENTIAL PEPTIDOMIMETICS**
Katarzyna Koroniak-Szejn, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland
Katarzyna Salamon-Krokosz, Karolina Paszek, Henryk Koroniak

MATERIALS - 03

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Gasper Tavcar, Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

- 9:20 - 9:40 **FLUOROANNULATION OF POLYCYCLIC (HETERO)AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS**
Olga Boltalina, Colorado State University, United States of America
Steven Strauss, Colin Brook, Kerry Rippey
-
- 9:40 - 10:00 **HIGHLY FLUORINATED G-C₃N₄ FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC APPLICATIONS**
Bonnet Pierre, ICCF - Université Clermont Auvergne, France
-
- 10:00 - 10:20 **IMPACT OF THE PROPERTIES OF SUPPORTS IN THE SYNTHESIS OF MGF₂ BASED CATALYST. GAS-PHASE FLUORINATION OF CHLORINATED ORGANIC MOLECULES AS AN APPLICATION.**
Julien Dieu, IC2MP CNRS, France
Yawen Wang, Amandine Guiet, Vincent Maisonneuve, Marc Dubois, Sylvette Brunet
-

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 11

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Hikaru Yanai, School of Pharmacy, Tokyo University of Pharmacy and Life Sciences, Japan

- 9:20 - 9:40 **DIFLUOROSILICATES AND DIFLUOROIMIDAZOLES, EFFECTIVE REAGENTS FOR SECONDARY SUBSTRATES AND ACTIVATED PHENOLS**
Jaroslav Kvicala, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic
Sarka Bouzkova, Michal Trojan, Adam Hroch, Vít Jeníček, Evelin Gruden, Gasper Tavcar, Jernej Iskra, Marketa Rybackova
-
- 9:40 - 10:00 **CHIRAL AMMONIUM-OXOCARBENIUM DICATIONS IN SUPERACID: REMOTE DIASTERESELECTIVE FUNCTIONALIZATION OF NON-ACTIVATED ALKENES**
Emanuela Berrino, Université de Poitiers, UMR-CNRS 7285, IC2MP, France
Thomas Cantin, Maxime Artault, Frédéric Guégan, Cassandra Vitse, Agnès Martin-Mingot, Sébastien Thibaudeau
-
- 10:00 - 10:20 **SYNTHESIS OF N-FLUOROALKYLATED KETENIMINES AND THEIR APPLICATION**
Anna Kubickova, Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic
Svatava Voltrova, Petr Beier
-

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 12

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Junji Ichikawa, Sagami Chemical Research Institute, Japan

11:00 - 11:20 **FLUORINATED ORGANIC AZIDES: STABLE AND VALUABLE BUILDING BLOCKS IN SYNTHESIS**
Petr Beier, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Czech Republic

11:20 - 11:40 **ELECTROPHILIC SUBSTITUTION AT C5 POSITION OF FLUORINATED ISOXAZOLINES WITH C-F BOND CLEAVAGE**
Kazuyuki Sato, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Setsunan University, Japan
Tomohiro Kuroki, Yukiko Karuo, Atsushi Tarui, Kentaro Kawai, Masaaki Omote

11:40 - 12:00 **DIRECT TRIFLUOROMETHOXYLATION OF ARYNES USING 2,4'-DINITRO(TRIFLUOROMETHOXY)BENZENE AS TRIFLUOROMETHOXIDE ANION SOURCE**
Lilian Wisson, Laboratoire d'Innovation Thérapeutique et Application, UMR7042, France
Fabien Toulgoat, Thierry Billard, Gilles Hanquet, Armen Panossian, Frédéric Leroux

12:00 - 12:20 **ISOLATION AND APPLICATION OF TRIFLUOROMETHYL ISOBENZOFURANS**
Hideki Amii, Gunma University, Japan

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 06

ROOM: 207

Chair: Benoît Crousse, University Paris Saclay-CNRS BioCIS UMR 8076, France

- 11:00 - 11:20 **FLUORINATED AMINOPHOSPHONATES AND CARBOHYDRATES - VERSATILE SYNTHETIC UNITS**
Henryk Koroniak, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland
Marcin Kazmierczak, Monika Bilska-Markowska, Katarzyna Koroniak-Szejn, Joanna Tomaszewska, Katarzyna Salamon-Krokosz, Karolina Paszek
-
- 11:20 - 11:40 **ORGANOCATALYTIC ENANTIOSELECTIVE SYNTHESIS OF ALPHA-MONOFUORO-ALPHA-AMINO ACID DERIVATIVES**
Satoru Arimitsu, University of the Ryukyus, Japan
-
- 11:40 - 12:00 **ALPHA,ALPHA-DIFLUORO-BETA-LACTAMS AS BUILDING BLOCKS FOR ONE-POT RING-OPENING PEPTIDE/ESTER/THIOESTER SYNTHESSES**
Masaaki Omote, Graduate School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Setsunan University, Japan
Yukiko Karuo, Kazuyuki Sato, Kentaro Kawai, Masaaki Omote
-
- 12:00 - 12:20 **STEREOSELECTIVE SYNTHESIS OF FLUOROALKENE DIPEPTIDE ISOSTERS**
Kazutaka Shibatomi, Toyohashi University of Technology, Japan
-

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 07

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Florian Kraus, Philipps-Universität Marburg, Fluorchemie, Germany

- 11:00 - 11:20 **TOWARDS INNOCENT DEELECTRONATION IN INNOCENT SOLVENTS**
Ingo Krossing, Albert-Ludwigs-University, Germany
-
- 11:20 - 11:40 **AN AMORPHOUS LEWIS-ACIDIC ZIRCONIUM CHLORO FLUORIDE AS HF SHUTTLE: C-F BOND ACTIVATION AND FORMATION**
Christian Heinekamp, Federal Institute for Material Research and Testing and Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Ana Guilherme Buzanich, Mike Ahrens, Thomas Braun, Franziska Emmerling
-
- 11:40 - 12:00 **HIGHLY REACTIVE MOLECULES AND MOLECULAR IONS IN LABORATORY AND SPACE**
Andreas Kornath, F-Select GmbH, Germany
Dirk Hollenwäger, Christoph Jessen, Sebastian Steiner
-
- 12:00 - 12:20 **SUPERACIDIC SYSTEMS BASED ON PENTAFLUORO-ORTHOTELLURATE DERIVATIVES AND THEIR REACTION PRODUCTS**
Sebastian Riedel, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
-

Thursday

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 13

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Gavin Chit Tsui, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

11:00 - 11:20 **CATALYZED AND NON-CATALYZED STRATEGIES FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF EMERGING FLUORINATED MOTIFS**

Anis Tlili, CNRS-University Lyon 1, France

11:20 - 11:40 **BTMP - A PRACTICAL REAGENT FOR RADICAL TRIFLUOROMETHOXYLATION REACTIONS**

Lilian Maria Maas, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Paul Golz, Sebastian Riedel, Matthew N. Hopkinson

11:40 - 12:00 **CU-CATALYZED DIFLUOROMETHYLATION REACTIONS**

Wei Liu, University of Cincinnati, United States of America

12:00 - 12:20 **TMSCF2BR: A PRIVILEGED DIFLUOROMETHYLENE TRANSFER REAGENT**

Chuanfa Ni, Shanghai Institute of Organic Chemistry, China
(People's Republic of)
Jinbo Hu

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 14

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Glenn Sammis, University of British Columbia, Canada

13:40 - 14:00 **PERFLUOROCUBANE: A NOVEL ELECTRON ACCEPTOR MOLECULE**

Midori Akiyama, Kyoto University, Japan

14:00 - 14:20 **SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, AND REACTIVITY OF NOVEL FLUORINATED CAGE COMPOUNDS**

Markus Etzkorn, University of North Carolina at Charlotte, United States of America
Alyssa Fediuk, Jamie Thuan, Dakota Hiller

14:20 - 14:40 **FLUORINATED STABLE CARBANIONS AS SUBSTITUENTS FOR CONTROLLING THE SOLUBILITY PROFILES OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS**

Hikaru Yanai, Tokyo University of Pharmacy and Life Sciences, Japan

Thursday

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY - 07

ROOM: 207

Chair: Denis Giguère, Université Laval, Canada

13:40 - 14:00 **AN IMPROVED COMMERCIAL SYNTHESIS OF BELZUTIFAN (MK-6482)**
Scott McCann, Merck Process Chemistry, United States of America

14:00 - 14:20 **EFFICIENT MANUFACTURING PROCESS FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF COVALENT KRAS G12C INHIBITOR GDC-6036**
Nicholas White, Genentech, United States of America

14:20 - 14:40 **FLUORINATED OLIGOSACCHARIDES PREPARED BY AUTOMATED GLYCAN ASSEMBLY AS TOOLS FOR CARBOHYDRATE-BASED MATERIAL SCIENCE**
Peter H. Seeberger, Max-Planck Institute for Colloids and Interfaces, Germany

MATERIALS - 04

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Alain Demourgues, ICMCB-CNRS-University of Bordeaux, France

13:40 - 14:00 **FROM MILD HYDROTHERMAL TO HIGH TEMPERATURE SOLUTIONS: STRATEGIES FOR SYNTHESIZING INORGANIC FLUORIDES**
Hans-Conrad Zur Loye, University of South Carolina, United States of America

14:00 - 14:20 **SOLID-STATE CHEMISTRY OF INORGANIC FLUORIDES : FROM TUNGSTEN-BRONZE TYPES TO FUNCTIONALIZED NANOFLUORIDES**
Alain Tressaud, CNRS-University of Bordeaux, France

14:20 - 14:40 **UNVEILING THE M-F/OH BONDING AND THE ANIONIC ORDERING IN MG, ZN, CU-BASED HYDROXYFLUORIDES FOR THE DESIGN OF BASIC CATALYSTS**
Helies Boumali, ICMCB-CNRS, France

Thursday

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 08

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Ingo Krossing, Institut für Anorganische und Analytische Chemie
and Freiburg Materials Research Center FMF, Germany

13:40 - 14:00 **SUSTAINABLE FLUORINE COMPOUNDS OF GROUPS 13 AND 14 ELEMENTS**
Herbert W. Roesky, Institute of Inorganic Chemistry University of
Göttingen, Germany

14:00 - 14:20 **NOVEL ORGANYLFLUOROCYANOBORATES: SYNTHESSES AND
APPLICATION**
Nils Schopper, Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Institute for
Sustainable Chemistry & Catalysis with boron (ICB), University of
Wuerzburg, Germany
Maik Finze

14:20 - 14:40 **ARYLDIFLUOROBORANES: SYNTHESSES, STRUCTURES, AND REACTIVITY**
Douglas Turnbull, McGill University, Canada
Marc-André Légaré

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 15

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Thierry Lequeux, UNIVERSITE CAEN LCMT, France

15:20 - 15:40 **RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN THE PREPARATION OF MOLECULES
MERGING FLUORINE AND CHALCOGEN ATOMS**
Emmanuel Magnier, Institut Lavoisier de Versailles, France

15:40 - 16:00 **BENZODITHIAZOLES-SULFOXIMINES : SYNTHESSES OF NEW
POWERFUL RADICAL PERFLUOROALKYLATING AGENTS**
Elsa Anselmi, Institut Lavoisier de Versailles, France
Guillaume Dagousset, Samir Messaoudi, Emmanuel Magnier, Elsa Anselmi

16:00 - 16:20 **BENZOTHIAZOLIUM SALTS AS REAGENTS FOR ORGANOFUORINE
CHEMISTRY**
Matthew N. Hopkinson, Newcastle University, United Kingdom
Stefan Dix, Matteo Tironi, Lilian Maria Maas, Alex Haswell

Thursday

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 16

ROOM: 207

Chair: Christine Le, York University, Canada

15:20 - 15:40 **SYNTHESIS OF N-FLUORINATED SCAFFOLDS AND ACCESS TO NEW COMPOUNDS**

Benoît Crousse, CNRS-University Paris Saclay, France

15:40 - 16:00 **INTRODUCTION OF FLUOROALKYL GROUPS INTO AROMATIC RINGS VIA TRANSIENT DIARYLIODONIUM(III) SALTS**

Kotaro Kikushima, Ritsumeikan University, Japan

Kohei Yamada, Tomoka Tsuda, Yasuyuki Kita, Toshifumi Dohi

16:00 - 16:20 **SYNTHESIS OF TERTIARY ALKYL FLUORIDES BY HYDROFLUORINATION OF ALKENES AND DEOXYFLUORINATION OF ALCOHOLS**

Xavier Bertrand, Université Laval, Canada

Mathieu Pucheault, Laurent Chabaud, Jean-François Paquin

MATERIALS - 05

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Hans-Conrad zur Loye, University of South Carolina, United States Of America

15:20 - 15:40 **TWO-DIMENSIONAL AG(II) SULFATE AND FLUORIDE ANTIFERROMAGNETS**

Mateusz Domanski, University of Warsaw, Poland

Zoran Mazej, Wojciech Grochala

15:40 - 16:00 **TOWARD MODULATING SOLID STATE STRUCTURES OF ORGANIC SEMICONDUCTOR MATERIALS THROUGH FLUORINATION AND PERFLUOROALKYLATION**

Haoran Sun, University of South Dakota, United States of America

16:00 - 16:20 **SOLID SOLUTIONS IN THE QUASI-BINARY AG(II)F₂/CU(II)F₂ PHASE DIAGRAM**

Daniel Jezierski, University of Warsaw, Centre of New Technologies, Poland

Kacper Koterwas, Piotr Polczynski, Mateusz Domanski, Zoran Mazej, José Lorenzana, Wojciech Grochala

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 09

ROOM: 2104AB

Chair: Udo Radius, Institute for Inorganic Chemistry, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany

15:20 - 15:40 **GALLATE AND INDATE SALTS WITH UNSATURATED ELECTRON WITHDRAWING GROUPS**

Berthold Hoge, Bielefeld University, Germany
Sven Porath, Katharina Tölke

15:40 - 16:00 **INTRODUCING A NEW ALUMINUM-BASED LEWIS SUPERACID: ALUMINUM TRIS(FLUOROSULFATE)**

Johanna Schlögl, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Simon Steinhauer, Sebastian Riedel

16:00 - 16:20 **ARSENIC TRIFLUORIDE. A CONVENIENT, LITTLE KNOWN FLUORINATING AGENT**

Attila E. Pavlath, Western Regional Research Center, United States of America

MOISSAN SESSION - DAVID O'HAGAN (MOISSAN PRIZE WINNER 2018) AND VÉRONIQUE GOUVERNEUR (MOISSAN PRIZE WINNER 2021) - SPONSORED BY OMEGACHEM

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Alain Tressaud, CNRS & Univ. Bordeaux, France

16:25 - 16:35 **POSTER PRIZES**

16:35 - 16:40 **INTRODUCTION (AWARD PRESENTATION)**

16:40 - 17:25 **RICH PICKINGS IN THE INTER-TIDAL ZONE BETWEEN HYDROCARBONS AND PERFLUOROCARBONS**

David O'Hagan, University of St Andrews, United Kingdom

17:25 - 18:10 **NEW WAYS TO DO FLUORINE CHEMISTRY**

Veronique Gouverneur, University of Oxford, United Kingdom

Thursday

Friday, July 28, 2023

PLENARY SESSION - SENSUKI OGOSHI (MASATO OHASHI) - SPONSORED BY ARKEMA INC.

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Joseph Thrasher, Clemson University, United States of America

8:15 - 9:00 **TRANSFORMATIONS OF TETRAFLUOROETHYLENE INTO POLYFLUORINATED ORGANIC COMPOUNDS USING TRANSITION-METAL COMPLEXES**
Masato Ohashi, Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan
Sensuke Ogoshi

9:00 - 9:15 **ISFC / ESFC**

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 17

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Cody Pitts, University of California, Davis, United States Of America

9:20 - 9:40 **STRATEGIES TOWARDS FLUOROALKYLATED BUILDING-BLOCKS FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION**
Frédéric Leroux, CNRS, France

9:40 - 10:00 **HEXAFLUOROISOBUTYLATION OF ENOLATES VIA A TANDEM REACTION**
Guillaume Compain, University of Bordeaux, CNRS, Bordeaux INP, CBMN, UMR 5248, Institut Européen de Chimie et Biologie, France
Aline Delamare, Guillaume Naulet, Sandeep Mummadi, Brice Kauffmann, Gilles Guichard

10:00 - 10:20 **INVESTIGATIONS ON NUCLEOPHILIC, CARBENOID AND RADICAL FLUOROALKYLATION AND RADICAL FLUOROALKOXYLATION PATHWAYS**
Surya Prakash, University of Southern California, United States of America
Vinayak Krishnamurti, Colby Barrett, Xanath Ispizua-Rodriguez, Socrates Munoz, Ziyue Zhu, Yijie Xu, Daniel Lin, Matthew Coe

10:20 - 10:40 **PERFLUORO-TERT-BUTYLATION WITH NEW REAGENTS**
Jinbo Hu, Shanghai Institute of Organic Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China (People's Republic of)
Qian Wang, Zhiqiang Wei

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY - 18

ROOM: 207

Chair: Dominique Cahard, CNRS, France

- 9:20 - 9:40 **MERGING FLUORINATED MOIETIES AND HETEROATOMS: OPPORTUNITIES IN EMERGING FLUORINATED GROUPS DESIGN**
Thierry Billard, CNRS-University of Lyon, France
-
- 9:40 - 10:00 **RAPID AND EFFICIENT FLUORINE INCORPORATION VIA SULFONE IMINIUM FLUORIDES**
Patrick Melvin, Bryn Mawr College, United States of America
James Vogel
-
- 10:00 - 10:20 **RHODIUM-CATALYZED INTRAMOLECULAR CYCLOPROPANATION OF TRIFLUOROMETHYL- AND PENTAFLUROSULFANYL- SUBSTITUTED ALLYLIC CYANODIAZOACETATES**
Lauriane Peyrical, Université de Montréal, Canada
Marie-Rose Ouellet-Du Berger, Maxim Boucher, Mélodie Birepinte, Jean-François Paquin, André Charette
-
- 10:20 - 10:40 **THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW ONE-POT SYNTHETIC METHODS USING SULFUR(IV) REAGENTS**
Glenn Sammis, University of British Columbia, Canada
-

MATERIALS - 06

ROOM: 2101

Chair: Marc Dubois, Clermont Auvergne University, France

- 9:20 - 9:40 **CHEMICAL CAPACITOR ' HOW FAR MAY ONE PUSH IT?**
Wojciech Grochala, University of Warsaw, Poland
Lukasz Wolanski, Piotr Szkudlarek, Daniel Jezierski, José Lorenzana
-
- 9:40 - 10:00 **IMPACTING HIGH-PRESSURE CONDITIONS OF STRUCTURAL TRANSITIONS IN ALKALI METAL FLUORIDES**
Kevin Lemoine, Institut de Chimie de Clermont-Ferrand, France
Yoshiyuki Inaguma
-
- 10:00 - 10:20 **MIXED-ANION COMPLEXES WITH A LARGE MAGNETIC ANISOTROPY OBTAINED BY FLUORIDE ABSTRACTION**
Alain Tressaud, CNRS-University of Bordeaux, France
-
- 10:20 - 10:40 **ORDER-DISORDER PHENOMENA AND MICROCRYSTALLINITY IN THE FLUORITE TYPE STRUCTURE WHEN SOME OF THE METAL IONS ARE SUBSTITUTED BY DIVALENT TIN**
Georges Denes, Concordia University, Canada
Abdualhafed Muntasar, M. Cecilia Madamba, Alena Peroutka, Zhimeng Zhu, Abdellatif Bensegueni, Hocine Merazig
-

Friday

PLENARY SESSION - THOMAS BRAUN - SPONSORED BY F-SELECT GMBH

ROOM: 2000A

Chair: Michael Gerken, University of Lethbridge, Canada

11:20 - 12:05 **METAL-MEDIATED DEFLUORINATION AND FLUORINATION PROCESSES TO ACCESS FLUORINATED ALKENES**

Thomas Braun, Humboldt-University of Berlin, Germany

Mike Ahrens, Gisa Meißner, Simon Racher, Stefan Sander, Maria Talavera, Cortney von Hahmann

CLOSING WORDS

ROOM: 2000A

12:05 - 12:20 **CLOSING WORDS**

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Poster Presentations

Monday, July 24, 2023

FROM 18:00 TO 20:00

-
- 02** **CLEAVABLE FLUOROUS TAGS FOR SOLUBILIZATION OF THERAPEUTIC DRUGS IN PERFLUOROCARBON NANOEMULSIONS**
Ethan Ng, UCLA, Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, United States of America
Ellen Sletten
-
- 03** **DEVELOPMENT OF SELECTIVE INHIBITORS TARGETING MULTI-ANTIMICROBIAL EXTRUSION TRANSPORTER TO OVERCOME ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE**
Susumu Shinya, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Setsunan University, Japan
Kentaro Kawai, Naoki Kobayashi, Yukiko Karuo, Atsushi Tarui, Kazuyuki Sato, Masato Otsuka, Masaaki Omote
-
- 04** **ENHANCING PHOTOSTABILITY AND BRIGHTNESS OF FLUOROUS CYANINE DYES FOR BIOLOGICAL IMAGING VIA COUNTERION EXCHANGE**
Helen Lin, University of California, United States of America
Eric Lin, Ellen Sletten
-
- 05** **FLUORINATED FOLDAMERS CONTAINING N-DIFLUOROMETHYL-TRIAZOLE SCAFFOLD**
Benoît Crousse, CNRS-University Paris Saclay, France
-
- 06** **IN VITRO EVALUATION OF THREE RADIOFLUORINATED TRACERS FOR PET IMAGING OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE**
Faustine d'Orchymont, CAMH, Canada
Andrea Narvaez, Roger Raymond, Stephen Krause, Neil Vasdev
-
- 07** **MORPHOLINE-MEDIATED DEFLUORINATIVE CYCLOADDITION OF GEM-DIFLUORO ALKENES AND ORGANIC AZIDES**
Mario Djugovski, University of Mississippi, United States of America
Tzu-Yu Huang, Destinee Manning, Sweta Adhikari, Sudeshna Roy
-
- 08** **PET IMAGING OF HDACS IN THE BRAIN USING SILICON-FLUORIDE ACCEPTORS**
En Zhao, McGill University, Canada
-

- 09** **BIOMASS-DERIVED ACTIVATED CARBONS FOR THE RECLAMATION OF FLUORINATED GASES**
Ana B. Pereiro, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal
Julio E. Sosa, Rui P. P. L. Ribeiro, Inês Matos, Maria Bernardo, Isabel M. Fonseca, José P. B. Mota, João M. M. Araújo
-
- 10** **CUSTOM FLUOROUS SURFACTANTS FOR IMPROVING FORCE SENSING MICRODROPLETS**
Joseph Garcia, Univeristy of California, Los Angeles, United States of America
Heidi van de Wouw, Yucen Liu, Jennifer Pollock, Otger Campàs, Ellen Sletten
-
- 11** **DEVELOPMENT OF MANUFACTURING ATMOSPHERIC PRESSURE PTFE PYROLYSIS MONOMER AND LINEAR PFPE MATERIAL MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGY**
Yuk Duck Soo, EURAMA, South Korea
Park Jae Hyung, Ryu Jung Bok
-
- 12** **MACROMOLECULAR CROWDING AS AN INTRACELLULAR STIMULUS FOR RESPONSIVE POLYOXAZOLINE NANOMATERIALS**
Paige Kotowitz, University of California, Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, United States of America
Daniel Estabrook, John Chapman, Shuo-Ting Yen, Helen Lin, Ethan Ng, Linglan Zhu, Heidi van de Wouw, Otger Campàs, Ellen Sletten
-
- 13** **REMOVAL OF PERFLUOROOCCTANOIC ACID FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS USING IONIC LIQUIDS AND POROUS SOLID MATRICES**
María C. Naranjo, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal
Inês Matos, Maria Bernardo, Isabel M. Fonseca, João M. M. Araújo, Ana B. Pereiro
-
- 14** **STABILITY IN PLASMA OF ALOXFY AND YOXYF THIN FILMS DEPOSITED BY ATOMIC LAYER DEPOSITION**
Bon Jung Koo, Sungkyunkwan University, Department of Semiconductor and Display Engineering, South Korea
-
- 15** **ADVENTURES IN ORGANOSILICON FLUORIDE ELIMINATION**
Guillaume Bélanger-Chabot, Université Laval, Canada
Gabriela Arias-Garcia, Houari Dahmani, Alexandre Poirier, Louis-Philippe Poulin
-
- 16** **ELECTROCHEMICAL FLUORINATION - A VERSATILE TOOL FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF FLUORINATED BUILDING BLOCKS**
Tanja Knuplez, University of Wuerzburg, Germany
Leon N. Schneider, Younes K. J. Bejaoui, Kristina A. M. Maibom, Nikolai V. Ignat'ev, Maik Finze
-

- 17** **FLUORINATED ALKYLCHLORONIUM CATIONS: POWERFUL ELECTROPHILIC ALKYLATING REAGENTS**
Lukas Fischer, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Sebastian Riedel
-
- 18** **FROM XEF₂ TO RADICAL CATIONS OF BIPHENYLDERIVATES**
Konstantin Kloiber, Albert-Ludwigs-University, Germany
-
- 19** **LEWIS ACIDITY OF MOLYBDENUM FLUORIDES**
Miriam van Hoeve, University of Lethbridge, Canada
Janelle Bykowski, Jacob Challenger, Rachael Bell, Felix O'Donnell,
Stacey Wetmore, Michael Gerken
-
- 20** **LIGAND-INDUCED AUTOIONIZATION OF MOOF₄ AND WOF₄**
Craig Sommer, University of Lethbridge, Canada
Stacey Wetmore, Michael Gerken
-
- 21** **MOOF₄ AS A PRECURSOR FOR OXYFLUORIDOMOLYBDATES(VI)**
Tobias Burghardt Wassermann, Philipps-Universität Marburg,
Germany
Florian Kraus
-
- 22** **NEW PERFLUORINATED SILVER(I) ALCOHOLATES - VERSATILE TRANSFER REAGENTS**
Paul Golz, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Marius Balizs, Helen Kemmler, Merlin Kleoff, Patrick Vossnacker,
Sebastian Riedel
-
- 23** **PLATINUM-CATALYZED HYDROFLUORINATION OF ALKYNES: HYDROGEN BONDING TO INDOLYLPHOSPHINE LIGANDS TO PROVIDE FLUORIDE REACTIVITY**
Ouchan He, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
-
- 24** **REACTIVITY OF BIURET IN SUPERACIDIC MEDIA**
Martin Regnat, LMU Munich, Germany
-
- 25** **REACTIVITY OF RHODIUM (I) HYDRIDE COMPLEX TOWARDS FLUORINATED OLEFINS AND ETHERS**
Soodeh Mollasalehi, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
-
- 26** **REACTIVITY OF RHODIUM COMPLEXES TOWARDS SULFUR FLUORIDES**
Ruben Jaeger, Humboldt-University of Berlin, Germany
Thomas Braun
-
- 27** **REACTIVITY OF WF₆ TOWARDS TRIDENTATE LIGANDS**
Taylor Adamitz, University of Lethbridge, Canada
Felix O'Donnell, Stacey Wetmore, Michael Gerken
-

- 28 **SPACE MOLECULES IN SUPERACIDIC MEDIA**
Dirk Hollenwäger, Ludwig-Maximilian University, Germany
Niklas Kölbl, Daniela Staudacher, Valentin Bockmair, Andreas J. Kornath
-
- 29 **SYNTHESIS AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF HYBRID COMPOUNDS
BASED ON TIN(IV) : COMPARISON OF THE FLUORIDES WITH
THE CHLORIDES**
Georges Denes, Concordia University, Canada
Georges Denes, Rochdi Ghallab, Rima Gheribi, Abdellatif Bensegueni
-
- 30 **SYNTHESIS AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF THE HCO⁺ CATION**
Sebastian Steiner, Ludwig-Maximilian University, Germany
Christoph Jessen, Valentin Bockmair, Alan Virmani, Andreas J. Kornath
-
- 31 **SYNTHESIS OF A FERROCENE DECA- AND UNDECACATION**
Susanne Margot Rupf, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Amina Leoni Moshtaha, Moritz Malischewski
-
- 32 **THE STRUCTURE OF HYDROXYMETHANESULFONIC ACID**
Valentin Bockmair, LMU Munich, Germany
-
- 33 **TIN(II)-FLUORINE BONDING IN A CHLORIDE FLUORIDE MATRIX:
CHANGE OF BONDING TYPE FROM COVALENT TO FULLY IONIC AND
CHANGE OF BOND STRENGTH FROM NORMAL TO EXTREMELY WEAK**
Georges Denes, Concordia University, Canada
Georges Denes, Korzior Tam, Julie Kochuparampil, Abdellatif
Bensegueni, Hocine Merazig
-
- 34 **UNUSUAL STABILIZATION OF MONOVALENT INDIUM IN
OXYFLUORIDES LEADING TO TUNABLE LUMINESCENCE IN VISIBLE
RANGE**
Alizée Deslandes, COPL - Université Laval / ICMCB (U.Bordeaux),
Canada
Alassani Fouad, Leïlou Loiseau-Foucher, Stanislav Pechev, Véronique
Jubera, Mathieu Duttine, Etienne Durand, Younes Messaddeq, Thierry
Cardinal, Alain Demourgues
-
- 35 **AN AMORPHOUS TEFLATE DOPED ALUMINIUM CHLOROFLUORIDE**
Minh Bui, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Kurt Hoffmann
-
- 37 **ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE FLEXIBLE UHMWPE COMPOSITES
BASED ON PERFLUOROPOLYETHERS-FUNCTIONALIZED
CARBON-BASED FILLERS**
Davide Ceriotti, Politecnico Milano, Italy
-
- 38 **FREE STANDING FEF3 · 0.33 H₂O-LOADED CNTS BUCKYPAPER AS
CATHODE FOR HIGH PERFORMANCES LITHIUM BATTERIES**
Federico Maria Scesa, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
-

- 39** **PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BIOMASS-ACTIVATED CARBONS FOR THE ADSORPTION OF PFAS IN ENVIRONMENTAL WATER**
Ana B. Pereira, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal
Didier M. Rodríguez, Rafael Chambel, Guilherme Coelho, María C. Naranjo, Inês Matos, Maria Bernardo, Isabel M. Fonseca,
João M. M. Araújo
-
- 40** **RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF POLYMER ALLOY WITH NANO-DISPERSED FLUORORESIN**
Takuma Maruhashi, DAIKIN INDUSTRIES, Japan
-
- 41** **SINGLET OXYGEN RESPONSIVE SURFACTANTS FOR TARGETED PAYLOAD DELIVERY IN PERFLUOROCARBON NANOEMULSIONS**
Linglan Zhu, University of California, United States of America
Sangeeta Kelkar, Ellen Sletten
-
- 42** **THE REVERSIBILITY OF FLUORINATED GRAPHITE IN SOLVENT-FREE LITHIUM BATTERY**
Marie Colin, Université Clermont Auvergne, France
Katia Guérin, Killian Henry, Elodie Petit, Marc Dubois
-
- 43** **WITH FLUORINE TO METHANOL CATALYSTS FOR SUSTAINABLE CO₂-HYDROGENATION**
Henrik Schuster, Materials Research Center, University of Freiburg, Germany
Ingo Krossing
-
- 44** **A NOVEL SYNTHETIC METHOD FOR POLYFLUOROALKANESULFONYL CHLORIDES**
Koichi Murata, Materials Integration Laboratories, AGC Inc, Japan
-
- 45** **ALDIMINIUM-BASED POLY(HYDROGEN FLUORIDE) AND ASSOCIATED NEUTRAL COMPOUNDS**
Evelin Gruden, Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
Jaroslav Kvicala, Gasper Tavcar
-
- 46** **ALLYLIC DIFLUORIDES AS ACCEPTORS OF PHOTOGENERATED RADICALS: A ROUTE TO MONOFLUOROALKENES VIA C-F ACTIVATION**
Taylor Semeniuk, University of Lethbridge, Canada
Ty Dudas, Jean-Denys Hamel
-
- 48** **CHLORO IMIDAZOLIUM-BASED REAGENT FOR DEOXYFLUORINATION**
Grisa Princic, Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Slovenia
Jan Jelen, Blaz Omahen, Evelin Gruden, Gasper Tavcar, Jernej Iskra
-
- 49** **CYCLIC DIKETONE RING OPENING VIA FLUORINATION AND SUCCESSIVE CARBON-CARBON BOND CLEAVAGE**
Yusuke Yoto, Ritsumeikan University, Japan
Hideyasu China, Hiroataka Sasa, Kotaro Kikushima, Toshifumi Dohi
-

- 50** **DEVELOPMENT OF RECOVERABLE AND REUSABLE REAGENTS FOR AROMATIC TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION**
Akari Matsuoka, Gunma University, Japan
Mizuki Kita, Tsuyuka Sugiishi, Hideki Amii
-
- 51** **ENANTIOSELECTIVE REDUCTION OF PROCHIRAL ALPHA-CF₃ AND ALPHA-SF₅ KETONES**
Kelly Burchell-Reyes, Université Laval, Canada
Jean-François Paquin
-
- 52** **EXPLORATION TOWARD THE SYNTHESIS OF ALIPHATIC SF₅-CONTAINING COMPOUNDS USING THE KOLBE REACTION**
Vincent Mastalerz, Université Laval, Canada
Kevin Lam, Jean-François Paquin
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